

Validation of 3-D printed vascular models for simulation training

1. What is your current role?

Registrar (ST3-ST8) — Vascular surgery	
Registrar (ST3-ST8) — General surgery	
Consultant - Vascular Surgery	
Consultant – General Surgery	
Other (please specify)	

2. How confident are you in performing a complete open vascular end-to-side anastomosis?

Not at all confident	
Confident to describe the basic steps but not the practical application	
Confident to perform parts of the procedure with supervision	
Confident to complete the whole procedure with supervision	
Confident to complete the whole procedure without assistance or supervision	

3. How many times have you performed a **complete** open end-to-side vascular anastomosis (from arteriotomy to closure) on a patient in theatre?

Trainees may include procedures with supervisor-trainer scrubbed or unscrubbed

Never	
0-10	
11-25	
25-50	
>50	

4. Please score the **double layer arterial model** in each of the following domains *for use in simulation training*
(circle the NUMBER which best applies)

Elasticity									
Not elastic enough			About right				Too elastic		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Rigidity									
Not rigid enough			About right				Too rigid		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Thickness									
Not thick enough			About right				Too thick		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Resistance to needle insertion when suturing									
Not enough resistance			About right				Too much resistance		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Resistance to pulling suture through									
Not enough resistance			About right				Too much resistance		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Tactile feel									
Not realistic								Very realistic	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Handling with instruments									
Not realistic								Very realistic	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Response to making an arteriotomy									
Not realistic								Very realistic	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Ability to hold a suture									
Not realistic								Very realistic	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Ability to hold tension of a knot									
Not realistic								Very realistic	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

5. What is your overall impression of the **arterial model** for simulation training?

Excellent	
Very good	
Good	
Equivocal	
Poor	
Very poor	

6. Compared to other models used for vascular anastomosis simulation (porcine aorta, synthetic rubber tube etc), how would you rate the **arterial model**?

Excellent	
Very good	
Good	
Equivocal	
Poor	
Very poor	
No previous experience with other arterial anastomosis models	

7. If used, how would you judge the **single layer artery** compared to the **double layer artery** for anastomosis simulation training for junior surgical trainees?

More acceptable	
As acceptable	
Not as acceptable	

8. Please rate the **vein model** in each of the following domains *for use in simulation training*
(circle the NUMBER which best applies)

Elasticity									
Not elastic enough			About right				Too elastic		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Rigidity									
Not rigid enough			About right				Too rigid		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

Thickness									
Not thick enough			About right				Too thick		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Resistance to needle insertion when suturing									
Not enough resistance			About right				Too much resistance		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Resistance to pulling suture through									
Not enough resistance			About right				Too much resistance		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Tactile feel									
Not realistic								Very realistic	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Handling with instruments									
Not realistic								Very realistic	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Ability to hold a suture									
Not realistic								Very realistic	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Ability to hold tension of a knot									
Not realistic								Very realistic	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10

9. What is your overall impression of the **vein model** for simulation training?

Excellent	
Very good	
Good	
Equivocal	
Poor	
Very poor	

10. Do you think these models are suitable to use for vascular anastomosis simulation training for vascular surgery trainees?

Yes	
No	

11. If no, what needs to be improved?

12. Any other comments, including anything you thought was particularly good?

Thank you for taking the time to participate in this study